

Table 1. Yield of RAU4045-2A (IET9790) in the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project during 1985 and 1986.

Variety	1985 yield (t/ha)							1986 yield (t/ha)					
	Titabar	Hazaribagh	Kanke	Faizabad	Coimbatore	Pondicherry	Mean	Chiplima	Arudhatinagar	Kanke	Faizabad	Mean	Mean days to 50% flowering
RAU4045-2A	1.6	3.7	3.5	3.5	5.0	4.4	3.6	1.7	2.5	4.3	3.6	3.0	59
Akashi (national check)	1.2	2.2	2.7	3.2	5.0	4.0	3.0	1.2	2.4	3.2	3.5	2.6	68
Cauvery	1.3	1.8	1.7	2.6	4.8	3.9	2.7	0.6	2.4	1.5	1.9	1.6	70
Local check	—	1.3	1.9	2.7	5.0	4.2	2.5	1.3	2.0	1.9	3.2	2.1	71
		(Brown Gora)	(Brown Gora)										
LSD (0.05)								0.7	0.7	0.7	0.5		

moderate resistance to bacterial blight and blast. It has a very short duration (80-85 d) and early vegetative vigor. It can survive a drought at the vegetative stage and is highly suited to drought-prone upland areas.

It has up to 125 grains/panicle and 1,000-grain weight is 23 g. Grain is short bold with high hulling (76%), milling (72%), and head rice recovery (63%). It has intermediate gelatinization temperature and gel consistency.

Mean yields of RAU4045-2A in regional experiments 1983-86 were 3.5 t/ha compared to Akashi, 2.4 t/ha, and Brown Gora, 2.1 t/ha.

In 1983-85 dryland testing, it yielded an average 2.5 t/ha against checks Bala (2.3 t/ha), Brown Gora (2.3 t/ha), and

Table 2. Average yields of RAU4045-2A in minikit testing in plateau region of Bihar, 1985-86.

District	Minikits (no.)	Average yield (t/ha)		Increase over Local Gora (%)
		RAU4045-2A	Local Gora	
Ranchi	61	1.6	1.3	23
Hazaribagh	45	2.1	1.7	24
Giridih	17	1.2	1.0	20
Palamau	28	1.5	1.2	25
Dhanbad	18	2.4	1.5	60
Total	169	1.8	1.3	31

Kiran (1.9 t/ha). In All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project experiments 1985, it yielded 3.6 t/ha over six locations, better than three other varieties; in 1986, it outyielded three other varieties, with a mean yield of 3.0 t/ha over four locations (Table 1).

In 1985-86 tests (169) RAU4045-2A, mean yield was 1.8 t/ha, compared to 1.34 t/ha for local Gora (Table 2). Mean yield in the International Rice Testing Program trials was 3.4 t/ha over 34 locations in 1982 and 3.5 t/ha over 56 locations in 1983. □

Sachiminori — a fine quality rice cultivar

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Sachiminori, a japonica introduced from Japan in 1982, has very high tillering ability, panicles/plant, and spikelet fertility, 1,000-grain weight of 26 g, and yields 6-7 t/ha. Grain quality is fine, with acceptable flavor. Percentage of brown rice is 82 and milled rice, 72-76. Sachiminori is highly resistant to blast and tolerant of drought, and has wide adaptability. When grown under the same conditions, inputs for Sachiminori are lower, yield higher and more stable,

and profit higher than those of most other cultivars.

In 1988, in the region that includes Beijing, Tianjing, and Hebei Provinces, more than 7,000 ha were planted to Sachiminori (renamed Xing Shi). In

recent years, eight other provinces have introduced Xing Shi, changing the early season cultivar choice from the original hsien (indica) rices to keng (japonica) rices. □

Stored grain infestation by Angoumois grain moth (AGM) in resistant and susceptible rice varieties

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We studied infestation by AGM *Sitotrogu cerealella* (Olivier) in the resistant CO 32 and susceptible CO 44 rice varieties in the insectary. Mylar film sheet cylinders (30 cm × 6 cm) were divided into 10 cross-sections, each 1 cm deep. Separate cylinders (in three replications) were filled with grains of CO 32 and CO 44 (number of grains in a section average 1,011). AGM eggs in a